

Rastafari of Jamaica

By Joseph Powell, University of Cambridge

Entry tags: Religious Group, Caribbean Religion, (Afro-)Caribbean religions, Syncretic Religions

As some Rastafari do not consider themselves a 'religious' group (as Western academic/theological discourse might describe it), the term 'livity' or 'movement' is more frequently employed to describe this Afrocentric belief system primarily composed of Afro-Caribbean adherents and those in the Afro-Caribbean diaspora. The Rastafari movement comprises a syncretic belief system combining Judeo-Christian tradition and imagery, African derived Jamaican peasant culture and spirituality, and a fierce political opposition to oppression and separation in favour of love and unity. Variation of practices, specific beliefs and spiritual influences, understood within Rastafari as 'livity', are broad within a movement which is deeply anti-hierarchical and which has no central spiritually authoritative body. The movement is however orientated around attestation to the divine, divinely inspired or personally inspirational nature of His Imperial Majesty (HiM) Haile Selassie I (pre-regnal name Ras Tafari), Emperor of Ethiopia from 1930-1974. Largely a monotheistic movement, adherents refer to the divine creator (sometimes interpreted as HiM) as 'Jah', an interpreted rendering of 'Jehovah'. Haile Selassie became a figure of anti-colonial resistance and black assertiveness in colonised communities across the world after his coronation in 1930 which some saw as fulfilment of prophecy foretold by black nationalist Marcus Garvey of a black king who would lead black populations out of oppression and towards glory. Garvey himself built much of his rhetoric of black self-determination around Biblical sentiments, particularly Biblical allusions to 'Ethiopia' (esp. Psalms 68:31) which was interpreted broadly to refer to Africa as a whole. Ethiopia had also gained a reputation as the only non-colonised sovereign state on the continent of Africa having previously defeated Italian imperialists (most significantly at the Battle of Adowa 1896, a date commemorated by Rastafari annually). Haile Selassie then came to embody an anti-imperialist and anti-oppressive struggle many in the Caribbean were experiencing, and become the central focus of a new movement. This led many in the movement both in its formation and today to yearn towards a repatriation to the 'motherland' of Africa, or more specifically for some to Ethiopia and to Shashamane where Haile Selassie donated land for the repatriative efforts of those in the diaspora. The notions here of resistance to oppression and injustice underpin Rastafari cosmologies and interactions with the world today. Rastafari frequently denounce the wickedness of 'Babylon' in contrast to 'Zion'. 'Babylon' offers an interpretation of the industrial, colonial and post-colonial, Western reality as a subjugation of humanity in an existence defined by oppression and suffering. Conversely, the most divine locality of Zion represents a beacon of hope, freedom and a physical and spiritual repatriation to the place of The Almighty. An equally core element of Rastafari belief is an emphasis on the natural and the primordial in recognition that that which is most natural on this earth is most in accord with Jah's original design for creation. This is conceptualised as 'ital' (from vital), a broad philosophical and ethical concept embodying a striving towards all in its most natural form. As some Rastafari do not consider themselves a 'religious' group (as Western academic/theological discourse might describe it), the term 'movement' is more frequently employed to describe this Afrocentric belief system primarily composed of Afro-Caribbean adherents and those in the Afro-Caribbean diaspora. The Rastafari movement comprises a syncretic belief system combining Judeo-Christian tradition and imagery, African derived Jamaican peasant culture and spirituality, and a fierce political opposition to oppression and separation in favour of love and unity. Variation of practices, specific beliefs and spiritual influences, understood within Rastafari as 'livity', are broad within a movement which is deeply anti-hierarchical, heterogenous and which has no central spiritually authoritative body. 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Early Rastafari, and indeed some still

today, grounded this divine assessment of His Majesty Biblically, referring to him under the titles of 'King of Kings, Lord of Lords', 'Conquering Lion of the Tribe of Judah',

Date Range: 1930 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Jamaica 1930-2020

Region tags: Latin America and the Caribbean, Caribbean, Jamaica

Contemporary Jamaica

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

DRAFT

- Source 1: Christensen, Jeanne 'Rastafari Reasoning and the RastaWoman: Gender Constructions in the Shaping of Rastafari Livity' (Lanham, MA: Lexington Books, 2014)
- Source 2: Edmonds, Ennis. Rastafari: A Short Introduction (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012)
- Source 3: Murrell, Nathaniel & Williams, Lewin 'The Black Biblical Hermeneutics of Rastafari' in Chanting Down Babylon: The Rastafari Reader (Philadelphia, PA: Temple University Press, 1998) pp326-349

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- Source 1: Chevannes, Barry 'Rastafari: Roots and Ideology' (Syracuse, NY: Syracuse University Press, 1994)
- Source 2: Homiak, John P 'Dub History: Soundings on Rastafari Livity and Language' in Rastafari and Other African-Caribbean Worldviews ed Chevannes, Barry (Basingstoke: Macmillan, 1998) pp127-176
- Source 3: Yawney, Carole Strictly Ital: Rastafari Livity and Holistic Health presented at the 9th annual meeting of the Society for Caribbean Studies, Hertfordshire (July 2-4 1985)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

DRAFT

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tDa-ewUSUGU>
- Source 1 Description: Rastafari theological discussion (reasoning) between two elders
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3UftuJpTLLw>
- Source 2 Description: Rastafari elder discussing natural living
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OQ4VS42sOLQ>
- Source 3 Description: Documentary exploring Rastafari livity

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: https://www.cifas.us/new/caribbean/most_strangest.html
- Source 1 Description: Biography of early Rastafari community figure Mortimo Planno
- Source 2 URL: <http://blog.raselijah.com/tag/rastafari-theology/>
- Source 2 Description: Blog exploring Rastafari theology

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

DRAFT

– Yes

Are they written:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Rastafari theology and thought is largely expressed orally through group 'reasoning' sessions. However, many Rastafari venerate the Bible as a text of divine wisdom, however there are also many who view it as a tool of oppression used to colonise Africa and to justify slavery. The 12 Tribes of Israel mansion place a particular emphasis on the Bible as a text containing divine

wisdom, generally encouraging members to read a Bible verse everyday. Other important texts include 'Selected Speeches' of Haile Selassie, 'Promised Key' by early Rastafari preacher/thinker Leonard Howell, and proto-Rastafari texts the 'Holy Piby' by Robert Athlyi Rogers and the 'Royal Parchment of Black Supremacy' by Fitz Balintine Pettersburg. In contemporary Jamaica there is also a growing trend amongst largely younger Rastafari to look towards Eastern texts for spiritual influence including Buddhist and Hindu texts.

Reference: Palmer, Delano Vincent. *Messianic 'I' and Rastafari in New Testament Dialogue: Bio-narratives, the Apocalypse, and Paul's Letter to the Romans*. University Press of America, 2010.

Reference: Murrell, Nathaniel, and Lewin Williams. "The Black Biblical Hermeneutics of Rastafari". In *Chanting down Babylon: The Rastafari Reader*, edited by Adrian McFarlane, Samuel Murrell, and William Spencer, 328-48. Philadelphia: Temple University Press, 1998.

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DRAFT

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Notes: Rastafari do not codified oral religious scriptures as such but Rastafari theology is formed and spiritualities shaped through group 'reasoning sessions in which a group of Rastafari will gather to discuss all aspects of Rastafari belief. These sessions sometimes involve sacramental use of ganja (cannabis), viewed by some as the 'holy herb' of the divine, to elevate participants consciousness to a higher plane of thought more in tune with the Almighty.

Reference: Homiak, John P.. "Dub History: Soundings on Rastafari Livity and Language". In *Rastafari and Other African-caribbean Worldviews*, 127-76. Macmillan, 1998.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: None specific to the Rastafari texts (Selected Speeches and Promised Key) beyond their status as divinely inspired. Biblical origin narratives applicable for those Rastafari who engage in Bible reading.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

DRAFT

– Yes

Reference: Rommen, Timothy. "Protestant Vibrations? Reggae, Rastafari, and Conscious Evangelicals". *Popular Music* 25, no. 2 (n.d.). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3877561>.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: There is a perception amongst some Jamaican Christians that Rastafari presents a competitive force in drawing youths away from the church and towards the Rastafari movement. The movement itself however is vehemently anti-evangelical and makes no active efforts to compete with other religious groups.

Reference: Price, Charles. *Becoming Rasta: Origins of Rastafari Identity in Jamaica*. New York University Press, 2009.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: This can vary as some Jamaican Christians can be very dismissive and disparaging towards a movement some see as illegitimate and without substance but most Jamaicans are respectful of the Rastafari and acknowledge their role in putting Jamaica on the cultural map. Rastafari themselves are generally accepting of other religious individuals in Jamaica but are highly critical of the structures and organisations which define them.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Contact is rarely neutral given the cultural prominence of Rastafari in Jamaica, most citizens have a view towards one end of the spectrum.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Violent persecution of Rastafari in Jamaica today is rare, however the group has previously suffered greatly at the hands of governmental agents and police forces (see esp. Coral Gardens Massacre 1963 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wpRAUCRJRi0>; https://www.jstor.org/stable/24384103?seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents)

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

DRAFT

– No

Is monumental religious architecture present:

DRAFT

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

DRAFT

– Field doesn't know

Notes: 29,026 according to 2011 census but many Rastafari refuse to provide census data to government agency's perceived to be oppressive. Anecdotal estimates gained during field work put's the number between 100,000-250,000.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Rastafari belief is viewed largely as a deeply personal journey and attestation which is in the hands of the individual. Different groups (mansions) do however have specific processes for inducting members. The three most prominent mansions in Jamaica are the 12 Tribes of Israel, the Nyabinghi Order and the Bobo Shanti. For 12 Tribes members admission involves statements of faith, a commitment to reading a passage of the Bible a day and the provision of a new which corresponds to the month the inductee was born in which corresponds to their new 'tribe' (Naphtali for January, Joseph for February, Benjamin for March). For Bobo Shanti, particularly those residing in permanent settlements such as the movements headquarters in Bull Bay, St Thomas (otherwise known as Lion Bay or Zion Hill) a demonstration of commitment to the group and an awareness of scripture and the groups codes is required to initiate. For the Nyabinghi historically a statement of faith and a commitment to the Nazarene vow of Numbers 6:5 was emphasised amongst members entering the order.

Reference: Barnett, Michael. "The Many Faces of Rasta: Doctrinal Diversity Within Rastafari". *Caribbean Quarterly* 51, no. 2 (June 15, 2005).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

DRAFT

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

DRAFT

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As per census data 1% of a total population of 2.9m, anecdotal estimates between 3% and 9%.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Rastafari are vehemently anti-evangelical and anti-proselytisation through an emphasis on the importance of an individual's distinctive spiritual journey

Does the religion have official political support

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Most Jamaican Rastafari are suspicious of political systems and structures which have been utilised to oppress Rastafari and other minorities for decades and centuries (often rendered as 'polytricks'). Individual Rastafari do hold government positions in Jamaica however, and previous attempts have been made towards greater Rastafari representation in politics (See Sam Brown's

Suffering People's Party <https://www.derekbishton.com/treatise-on-the-rastafarian-movement-by-samuel-elisha-brown/>)

Is iconography present:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Some public spaces

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari will frequently be seen with badges featuring imagery of Haile Selassie, Empress Menen Asfaw and Marcus Garvey most prominently although many other figures from music and culture are represented. Images of these nature are also commonly found in Rastafari homes and in Rastafari tabernacles (communal religious gathering spaces hosted traditionally in outdoor tents). Murals are also common as part of the facade of houses and dwellings or on urban walls. The Ethiopian colours of red, gold and green also feature prominently.

Reference: Rastafari and the Environment. "Rastafari Dwelling". Rastafari and the Environment, n.d. <https://caribbeanreligionuvm.files.wordpress.com/2012/04/p1010833.jpg?w=600&h=450CJDH1vHC8uoCFQAAAAAdAAAAABAJ>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Badge images and those in the home usually consist of photographs of those in question frequently featuring text or a quote superimposed (see attached images). Images can also feature those in Ethiopian Orthodox style. Distinctive mural artwork can also be seen in many parts of Jamaica.

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

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Specific to this answer:

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↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Rastafari emphasise the importance of an individual's journey to spiritual truth, and indeed many have moved from Rastafari towards the Ethiopian Orthodox faith of Haile Selassie.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari gather in tabernacles, open airy tent areas most commonly with a circular 'altar' type surface in the middle which features pictures and sacraments and from where those leading ceremonies speak. These also feature drums and sometimes sound system equipment. Prominent Jamaican tabernacles can be found in Pitfour and Scott's Pass.

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: There is no compulsion to pilgrimage but many Rastafari consider a journey to Ethiopia, be it temporary or more permanent, as a pilgrimage one should undertake. Some consider Zion to be the spiritual and literal home of Mount Zion, the ultimate yearned for destination.

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

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Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

DRAFT

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DRAFT

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L

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↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

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Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

DRAFT
– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

DRAFT
– No

Is iconography present:

DRAFT
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- On persons
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- Some public spaces

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Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

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Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Rastafari views on death have developed greatly since the movement's inception. It was a common belief for many in the movement in its first 40 or so years that a 'true' Rastafari could not die and both their physical and spiritual being would exist forever, stemming from a conception of Haile Selassie as the 'living God' and of Rastafari as a lifeful mentality for the living. It was only sinful and 'not true' Rastafari that would die. Given this many Rastafari would refuse to interact with the bodies of their fellow Rastafari, and would refuse to attend any funerals or events to mark passing. These views were particularly pronounced amongst Nyabingi Rastafari, and are still held by some. However, after the death of Bob Marley in 1981 and the reported death of Haile Selassie in 1975 (whom many believed would live eternally and indeed many believe is still alive) some in the movement began to move towards an understanding of death more in line with mainstream religions in which the spirit departs the body for a higher place, often rendered as Zion.

Reference: FIREFROMJAH. "Rastafari Funeral in the Barbados". YouTube, September 28, 2012. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SVrA2LiNtZg>.

Reference: BBC. "Living God's' Funeral Divides Rastas". BBC, November 5, 2000. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/world/africa/1007894.stm>.

↳

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: The spirit-mind is conceived by many as being the 'true' essence of the persons being whilst the body represents its physical vessel. It is often stated that whilst the body can be imprisoned and shackled the mind of a Rasta never can be.

Reference: Huhtala, Mari. "THE ONE IN THE MANY: Expressions of Rastafari Spirituality". Masters Thesis, Tampere University, 2015.

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

DRAFT

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Social norms vary greatly between Rastafari communities, although many Jamaican Rastafari groups have understandings of different social norms between men and women. Women are frequently expected to cover their bodies in a way considered 'modest' and not intended to cause arousal. This often includes covering of the dreadlocks/hair. Attitudes towards menstruating women also vary, with some groups considering this group 'unclean' and therefore unable to engage in ritualistic and domestic practices particularly the preparation of food. Some Bobo Shanti groups consider women to be 'unclean' both a week before and after a week long menstruation period and therefore unable to engage with the wider group for the entirety of this period. Some groups also enforce a practice of women being unable to fully take part in some ritualistic practices at all times of the month. Some consider women unable to be 'true' Rastafari in their own right and only able to join the movement through a man, or 'kingman'. This view can also be applied to female children in Rastafari groups with it considered the duty of the group to 'grow a dawta', meaning an emphasised effort to ensure a young girl is properly raised in the ways of Rastafari that is not applied to boys. Women are also considered unable to take part in wider group 'reasoning' sessions by some, restricting females to reasoning only with each other. In group 'binghi' celebrations some groups also restrict women from being able to play the drums during these celebrations instead allowing them to play a shaker instead. All of this varies greatly however, with women taking a much greater and equal role in all aspects of community life in some Rastafari communities.

Reference: Vernan Success. "Women in Rastafari Documentary". YouTube, August 14, 2013.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=onalpomCEGU>.

Reference: Christensen, Jeanne. Rastafari Reasoning and the Rastawoman. Lexington Books, 2014.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Rastafari_Reasoning_and_the_RastaWoman.html?hl=&id=CpJFAwAAQBAJ.

Reference: I Never Knew TV. "How to Dress Like a Rastafari Empress Youtube Video". YouTube, August 9, 2017. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WqGdR_4AcjU.

Are messianic beliefs present:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Haile Selassie is most frequently understood as a messianic figure sent to the earth to emancipate humanity from the sufferation, bondage and evil enforced by Babylon. For some this comes in a Christian understanding of Selassie as the second coming of Christ, whilst other's consider him to be earths first messiah. These groups also often link this to Haile Selassie's Solomonic heritage through the Ethiopian royal line which also connects him to King David. Many believe that after Haile Selassie's deposition as emperor in 1974 he is in a form of hiding somewhere either in this world or in another from where he will return in a second coming at some point in the future. Other's belief he is still present on earth in the much the same form as he was before. Some Rastafari would however reject this description of Haile Selassie as a Christian term which does reflect the divine nature of His Majesty, whilst other would suggest that Selassie was just a great man amongst men to have been on the earth (see linked video).

Reference: Hill, Robert A.. Dread History. Research Associates School Times, 2001.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Dread_History.html?hl=&id=SouBAAAACAAJ.

Reference: I Never Knew TV. "Prof-i on Haile Selassie Divine Status". YouTube, August 9, 2017.
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WqGdR_4AcjU.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Whilst Haile Selassie is a political figure his divine purpose is not understood as restoring political rule

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

DRAFT

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

DRAFT

– Yes

Reference: Wint, Eleanor. "Who Is Haile Selassie? His Imperial Majesty in Rasta Voices". In *Chanting down Babylon*, 159–66. Temple University Press, 1998.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Chanting_Down_Babylon.html?hl=&id=iesWzLHb_GUC.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Belief in the presence of a supreme high God is vastly prevalent across the movement in Jamaica. The form this takes varies greatly however, with some believing that Haile Selassie is the supreme high God, others that Selassie is a prophet/messiah figure under a greater supreme high god (Jah), and some believing that Selassie is not divine at all but one man under a supreme high God (Jah). Within the mansions these understandings also vary. Some 12 Tribes believe that the houses founder Prophet Gad belongs as part of triune supreme God understanding alongside Haile Selassie and Marcus Garvey. Some members consider Bob Marley also to have been a part of this trinity. For some Bobo Shanti members a triune understanding is also in place where the houses founder Prince/King Emmanuel occupies a place alongside Selassie and Marcus Garvey who is interpreted to be the second coming of John the Baptist by some. These formulations are less common amongst Nyabinghi members, with many considering Haile Selassie to embody the entire trinity in reference to the English translation of his regnal name (Power of the Trinity).

Reference: Edmonds, Ennis. "rastalogy' and 'livity: The Principles and Practices of Rastafari". In *Rastafari: A Very Short Introduction*. p32-52: Oxford University Press, n.d.

Reference: Barnett, Michael. "The Many Faces of Rasta: Doctrinal Diversity Within Rastafari". *Caribbean Quarterly* 51, no. 2 (n.d.).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Rastafari perceptions on this point are broad and heterogeneous. Some consider Haile Selassie to be the most high god alone, others consider him to be an anthropomorphic manifestation of a separate supreme high god. Historically Rastafari discussions of Jah and of Haile Selassie have referred to a 'living God', one amongst humanity on this earth in contrast to more traditionally Judeo-Christian concepts of a God distant from the earth. Discussions continue on this topic, although the reported death of Haile Selassie led some to reassess this description. An important and distinctive Rastafari theological concept also exists within these considerations of the divinity of the self. This is frequently articulated as Haile Selassie establishing the both the divinity of blackness and the divinity of humanity and the self through his status as the

'living God'. In this, the final I of Rastafari takes on a greater significance in indicating both the primordial nature of Haile Selassie as the 1st in a Roman numeral style but also as the first person singular pronoun in which it becomes a link with Selassie. This is most often expressed in the phrase 'InI', frequently taken to mean the I of Rastafari and the I of the self, indicating a link between the divinity of Rastafari and the divinity of the self. InI consciousness then represents a realisation of the self as a divinity anthropomorphised. The phrase is often used in conversation by many Rastafari in place of 'we' or 'us' to express both the divinity of the speaker and the unity of the speaker and the subject. This cosmological concept is visible in the Rastafari Iyarc dialect in which the first syllable sounds of words are replaced with an I sound such as Ital, Iration (creation) and perhaps most pertinently Inity (unity).

Reference: Powell, Joseph. "Ital Hermeneutics: The Innovative Theological Grounding of Rastafari Dietary (ietary) Practices (forthcoming Publication)". Black Theology, n.d..

Reference: Edmonds, Ennis B.. Rastafari: A Very Short Introduction. Oxford University Press, 2012.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Rastafari_A_Very_Short_Introduction.html?hl=&id=v8qte3BCDKcC.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Others take a more recognisably Judeo-Christian view in considering that the most high Jah is a diety which exists external from earth and who sent a divinely inspired messenger in the form of Haile Selassie to earth.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

DRAFT

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Quite literally the 'King of Kings' as Haile Selassie is frequently referred to is considered the supreme high god by many in the movement, whilst his wife Empress Menen Asfaw is considered divine alongside him though rarely elevated to the same level.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

DRAFT

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

DRAFT

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

DRAFT

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Almighty Jah is considered to be the ultimate form of love and justice.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

DRAFT

– Yes [specify]: A sense of the Almighty as a figure of justice and ensuring equality is central to Rastafari renderings of god.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Those who consider Haile Selassie to be the supreme high god recognise him to have ultimate knowledge of this world and to have had an deep and intimate knowledge of industry, agriculture, education and international relations. This is also considered alongside an omniscience as the original creator of all in creation, as it is for those who consider Jah and not Selassie to be the supreme high god.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

DRAFT

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

DRAFT

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Being true of heart and purpose in veneration of Jah is an important part of Rastafari worship. Those who are not considered to fulfill this are often said to have a 'bad mind wicked heart'.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

DRAFT

– Yes [specify]: As stated the Almighty (be it Selassie himself or a Jah figure above him) is considered to be omniscient

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: This like many aspects of Rastafari thought varies greatly but many consider Jah to be able to have ultimate efficacy in this world and all of creation

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Rastafari conceptions of God revolve centrally around a sense of Jah as a God of love, and love being synonymous with Jah. Love is viewed as one of the most powerful forces in the universe and as an essential force for equality between humanity and all aspects of creation. Ideas on this concept can be heard in Bob Marley's classic 'One Love'.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Whilst this may be a subjective determinable, Rastafari understandings of Jah and of live more fundamentally concern themselves only with positivity and positive energy. This is perhaps best encapsulated in the frequent refrain 'Forwards Ever, Backwards Never' conveying a desire only for forward progress.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Understandings of Haile Selassie as the supreme high God most frequently understand him as a human diety with human functions including hunger. It is frequently stated however that His Majesty ate in a self-effacing and understated manner, eating only small portions.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: A point that varies greatly between Rastafari, although fundamentally there is no person or 'body' to permit or disallow believers to worship anyone in a movement which places individual spirituality at the centre of importance. The Bobo Shanti mansion of Rastafari typically venerate their founder King Emmanuel whilst 12 Tribes Members also venerate their founder Prophet Gad with some viewing them as supernatural beings. Marcus Garvey is also worshipped by some as a supernatural being.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

DRAFT

– Yes [specify]: Conceptions of Haile Selassie frequently paint him as a warrior and a conqueror, a vanquisher of injustice of the armies of evil and colonialism.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Prayer and veneration of the most high is often understood as a communication process. Haile Selassie has also communicated with some Rastafari in person, most prominently during his visit to Jamaica in 1966.

↳ In dreams:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Personal revelation is a very important source of spiritual truths for many Rastafari, usually taking the form of dramatic visions received both when sleeping and when in a state of daydreaming.

↳ In trance possession:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Possession by spiritual forces was a feature of the earliest Rastafari communities, although these practices were largely expunged by a zealous form group known as the Youth Black Faith in the 1950's.

↳ Through divination practices:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Rastafari worship and the procedures with in it are open to all, although priests do play roles of varying significance between different groups.

↳ Only through monarch

DRAFT

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

DRAFT

– Yes [specify]: The sacramental consumption of ganja (cannabis) is frequently understood as a process which elevates human consciousness to higher plane where communication with the divine is made easier and less encumbered.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Whilst belief in the presence of human spirits is commonplace in Jamaica most Rastafari eschew this as a dangerous superstition which detracts from the true divine nature of creation. Again, spirit veneration and interaction with spirits was common amongst early Rastafari communities but this was expunged by the Youth Black Faith in the 1950's.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings are frequently understood in human terms, although understanding and renderings of Jah vary considerably.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Many Rastafari understand Haile Selassie as a mixed human-divine being, 'Christ in his kingly form' as it is often stated. In this rendering his attributes are considered synonymous with the most high supreme God as described above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Sacramental ganja (cannabis) consumption

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: As previously mentioned various groups may venerate different humans but veneration is most frequently limited to these humans.

Belief in afterlife:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Belief in the afterlife as it is commonly understood in Christian theology varies greatly. Many Rastafari do not ascribe to a belief in a heaven or hell where after life happens, believing instead that when the body dies the righteous souls will 'fly away home to Zion' a phrase often heard sung at Rastafari life commemorations. For many this remains a physical reality in this world, after Babylon has been toppled Zion will extend to the whole world ushering in a new world/cosmic order. Others subscribe to more traditionally Christian understanding of an afterlife, envisioning they will go to join Jah in a place other than this after their passing.

Reference: Chevannes, Barry. "Between the Living and the Dead: The Apotheosis of Rastafari Heroes". In *Religion, Diaspora, and Cultural Identity: A Reader in the Anglophone Caribbean*. Gordon and Breach, 1999.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: This is often described as Zion, variously and most commonly in reference to a physical Mount Zion located in Africa of this world or as a spiritual realm in another dimension.

Reference: Eyre, L. Alan. "Biblical Symbolism and the Role of Fantasy Geography Among the Rastafarians of Jamaica". *Journal of Geography* 84, no. 4 (January 1, 1985): 144-48.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: atest

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: atest

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: atest

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: atest

↳ Afterlife located in “other” space:

– Yes [specify]: Zion

Specific to this answer:
Region: atest

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

DRAFT
– Present and clear

Notes: Many Rastafari have an understanding of some moral absolutes existing, most primarily love, generosity and support for the oppressed in the face of evil and hatred. This is frequently framed around a search for balance in everything and achieving balance within oneself and the universe. The most fundamental force uniting these moral absolutes is a desire to be living in communion with nature and with the earth as Jah intended it. Through this communion both humanity and nature will flourish.

Reference: I Never Knew TV. “Ras Stimulant Discussing Balance with Nature”. YouTube, October 12, 2017. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LmFmNjlsXHE>.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Moral norms are most frequently attributed to the world order as put in place by Jah.

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

DRAFT
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

DRAFT
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

DRAFT
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

DRAFT

– Only one gender

– All individuals within society

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Large variance of beliefs on punishment meted out by supernatural beings. Many subscribe to a view that the unrighteous will meet their judgement in this world in a fiery blaze, whilst others subscribe to more traditionally Christian models that punishment will come in an afterlife.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jah is frequently understood as a God of justice and as the supreme arbiter. Implores are often made to Jah for the wicked to burn in a fiery damnation for their sins, particularly Babylon in the frequently heard phrase 'Babylon a burn'.

↳ Done only by high god:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

DRAFT

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Done randomly:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Other [specify]

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is meted out only to the wicked and evil doers.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Punishments in the after life aren't frequently emphasised by many Rastafari with an emphasis still very much in this realm. However many also have a more familiarly Judeo-Christian understanding of punishment in the afterlife.

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Other [specify]

DRAFT

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Divine punishment in this world is usually expressed through fire imagery with the understanding that the wicked can be met with immediate immolation by Jah if it is required. Punishment can be varied however with, effecting ones lot in life in different ways.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Other [specify]

DRAFT

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

DRAFT

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Jah is not generally understood as bestowing rewards as such, with a righteous life in communion with the Most High understand as a deeply rich and nourishing reward in itself. This varies however with some making direct appeals to Jah for rewards in their life.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Previously Rastafari corpses were left and completely unhandled by fellow Rastafari in the belief that only the unrighteous would die a physical death.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

DRAFT

– No

Are grave goods present:

DRAFT

– No

Are formal burials present:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Owing to the symbolic nature of fire and smoke within the movement many chose cremation over burial.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Understandings of the eschaton much like other aspects of Rastafari spirituality vary greatly. The movement has frequently been rendered as a millenarian group, but this description fails to capture the variety of interpretations amongst Rastafari. In a familiar Judeo-Christian framework some believe that the second coming of Haile Selassie will beckon in a judgement event in which the wicked are held to account for their evils and a new world order is enacted. In this, only the righteous will survive this event. Others believe that Selassie's presence on the earth represented the start of the eschaton in which the wicked are now held to account. Others still believe a super natural eschaton is unlikely and the earth and its residents will continue on its current trajectory. Between these positions are there countless other understandings of the end times.

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

Eschaton at some other time:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Other survival condition:
 - Yes [specify]: Many Rastafari state that it is only the truly righteous that will survive the judgement event

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Righteousness, love and an engagement in fighting the forces of wickedness and oppression are considered centrally important by many Rastafari. Alongside these generosity, unity, independence of thought and spirit, and peaceability are also highly venerated.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

DRAFT

– Yes

- ↳ Cooperation:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
DRAFT
– No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
DRAFT
– No
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

DRAFT

– Yes [specify]: Love and peaceability

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Rastafari views on death have developed greatly since the movements inception. It was a common belief for many in the movement in it's first 40 or so years that a 'true' Rastafari could not die and both their physical and spiritual being would exist forever, stemming from a conception of Haile Selassie as the 'living God' and of Rastafari as a lifeful mentality for the living. It was only sinful and 'not true' Rastafari that would die. Given this many Rastafari would refuse to interact with the bodies of their fellow Rastafari, and would refuse to attend any funerals or events to mark passing. These views were particularly pronounced amongst Nyabinghi Rastafari, and are still held by some. However, after the death of Bob Marley in 1981 and the reported death of Haile Selassie in 1975 (whom many believed would live eternally and indeed many believe is still alive) some in the movement begin to move towards an understanding of death more in line with mainstream religions in which the spirit departs the body for a higher place, often rendered as Zion.

Reference: FIREFROMJAH. "Rastafari Funeral in the Barbados". YouTube, September 28, 2012. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SVrA2LiNtZg>.

Reference: BBC. "Living God's' Funeral Divides Rastas". BBC, November 5, 2000. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/world/africa/1007894.stm>.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: The spirit-mind is conceived by many as being the 'true' essence of the persons being whilst the body represents it's physical vessel. It is often stated that whilst the body can imprisoned and shackled the mind of a Rasta never can be.

Reference: Huhtala, Mari. "THE ONE IN THE MANY: Expressions of Rastafari Spirituality". Masters Thesis, Tampere University, 2015.

Belief in afterlife:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Belief in the afterlife as it is commonly understood in Christian theology varies greatly. Many Rastafari do not ascribe to a belief in a heaven or hell where after life happens, believing instead that

when the body dies the righteous souls will 'fly away home to Zion' a phrase often heard sung at Rastafari life commemorations. For many this remains a physical reality in this world, after Babylon has been toppled Zion will extend to the whole world ushering in a new world/cosmic order. Others subscribe to more traditionally Christian understanding of an afterlife, envisioning they will go to join Jah in a place other than this after their passing.

Reference: Chevannes, Barry. "Between the Living and the Dead: The Apotheosis of Rastafari Heroes". In *Religion, Diaspora, and Cultural Identity: A Reader in the Anglophone Caribbean*. Gordon and Breach, 1999.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: This is often described as Zion, variously and most commonly in reference to a physical Mount Zion located in Africa of this world or as a spiritual realm in another dimension.

Reference: Eyre, L. Alan. "Biblical Symbolism and the Role of Fantasy Geography Among the Rastafarians of Jamaica". *Journal of Geography* 84, no. 4 (January 1, 1985): 144–48.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Zion

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

Reincarnation in this world:

DRAFT
– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Previously Rastafari corpses were left and completely unhandled by fellow Rastafari in the belief that only the unrighteous would die a physical death.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

DRAFT
– No

Are grave goods present:

DRAFT

– No

Are formal burials present:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Owing to the symbolic nature of fire and smoke within the movement many chose cremation over burial.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

DRAFT

– Yes

Reference: Wint, Eleanor. "Who Is Haile Selassie? His Imperial Majesty in Rasta Voices". In *Chanting down Babylon*, 159–66. Temple University Press, 1998.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Chanting_Down_Babylon.html?hl=&id=iesWzLHb_GUC.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Belief in the presence of a supreme high God is vastly prevalent across the movement in Jamaica. The form this takes varies greatly however, with some believing that Haile Selassie is the supreme high God, others that Selassie is a prophet/messiah figure under a greater supreme high god (Jah), and some believing that Selassie is not divine at all but one man under a supreme high God (Jah). Within the mansions these understandings also vary. Some 12 Tribes believe that the houses founder Prophet Gad belongs as part of triune supreme God understanding alongside Haile Selassie and Marcus Garvey. Some members consider Bob Marley also to have been a part of this trinity. For some Bobo Shanti members a triune understanding is also in place where the houses founder Prince/King Emmanuel occupies a place alongside Selassie and Marcus Garvey who is interpreted to be the second coming of John the Baptist by some. These formulations are less common amongst Nyabinghi members, with many considering Haile Selassie to embody the entire trinity in reference to the English translation of his regnal name (Power of the Trinity).

Reference: Edmonds, Ennis. "rastalogy" and 'livity: The Principles and Practices of Rastafari". In *Rastafari: A Very Short Introduction*. p32-52: Oxford University Press, n.d..

Reference: Barnett, Michael. "The Many Faces of Rasta: Doctrinal Diversity Within Rastafari". *Caribbean Quarterly* 51, no. 2 (n.d.).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Rastafari perceptions on this point are broad and heterogeneous. Some consider Haile Selassie to be the most high god alone, others consider him to be an anthropomorphic manifestation of a separate supreme high god. Historically Rastafari discussions of Jah and of Haile Selassie have referred to a 'living God', one amongst humanity on this earth in contrast to more traditionally Judeo-Christian concepts of a God distant from the earth. Discussions continue on this topic, although the reported death of Haile Selassie led some to reassess this description. An important and distinctive Rastafari theological concept also exists within these considerations of the divinity of the self. This is frequently articulated as Haile Selassie establishing the both the divinity of blackness and the divinity of humanity and the self through his status as the 'living God'. In this, the final I of Rastafari takes on a greater significance in indicating both the primordial nature of Haile Selassie as the 1st in a Roman numeral style but also as the first person singular pronoun in which it becomes a link with Selassie. This is most often expressed in the phrase 'InI', frequently taken to mean the I of Rastafari and the I of the self, indicating a link between the divinity of Rastafari and the divinity of the self. InI consciousness then represents a realisation of the self as a divinity anthropomorphised. The phrase is often used in conversation by many Rastafari in place of 'we' or 'us' to express both the divinity of the speaker and the unity of the speaker and the subject. This cosmological concept is visible in the Rastafari lyric dialect in which the first syllable sounds of words are replaced with an I sound such as Ital, Iration (creation) and perhaps most pertinently Inity (unity).

Reference: Powell, Joseph. "Ital Hermeneutics: The Innovative Theological Grounding of Rastafari Dietary (ietary) Practices (forthcoming Publication)". Black Theology, n.d..

Reference: Edmonds, Ennis B. *Rastafari: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford University

Press, 2012.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Rastafari_A_Very_Short_Introduction.html?hl=&id=v8qte3BCDKcC.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
DRAFT
– Yes
Notes: Others take a more recognisably Judeo-Christian view in considering that the most high Jah is a diety which exists external from earth and who sent a divinely inspired messenger in the form of Haile Selassie to earth.
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
DRAFT
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
DRAFT
– Yes
Notes: Quite literally the 'King of Kings' as Haile Selassie is frequently referred to is considered the supreme high god by many in the movement, whilst his wife Empress Menen Asfaw is considered divine alongside him though rarely elevated to the same level.
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
DRAFT
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
DRAFT
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
DRAFT
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
DRAFT
– Yes
Notes: Almighty Jah is considered to be the ultimate form of love and justice.
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
DRAFT
– Yes [specify]: A sense of the Almighty as a figure of justice and ensuring equality is central to Rastafari renderings of god.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
DRAFT
– Yes
Notes: Those who consider Haile Selassie to be the supreme high god recognise him to have ultimate knowledge of this world and to have had an deep and intimate knowledge of industry, agriculture, education and international relations. This is also considered alongside an omniscience as the original creator of all in creation, as it is for those who consider Jah and not Selassie to be the supreme high god.
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
DRAFT
– No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

DRAFT

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Being true of heart and purpose in veneration of Jah is an important part of Rastafari worship. Those who are not considered to fulfill this are often said to have a 'bad mind wicked heart'.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

DRAFT

– Yes [specify]: As stated the Almighty (be it Selassie himself or a Jah figure above him) is considered to be omniscient

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: This like many aspects of Rastafari thought varies greatly but many consider Jah to be able to have ultimate efficacy in this world and all of creation

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Rastafari conceptions of God revolve centrally around a sense of Jah as a God of love, and love being synonymous with Jah. Love is viewed as one of the most powerful forces in the universe and as an essential force for equality between humanity and all aspects of creation. Ideas on this concept can be heard in Bob Marley's classic 'One Love'.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Whilst this may be a subjective determinable, Rastafari understandings of Jah and of life more fundamentally concern themselves only with positivity and positive energy. This is perhaps best encapsulated in the frequent refrain 'Forwards Ever, Backwards Never' conveying a desire only for forward progress.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Understandings of Haile Selassie as the supreme high God most frequently understand him as a human deity with human functions including hunger. It is frequently stated however that His Majesty ate in a self-effacing and understated manner, eating only small portions.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: A point that varies greatly between Rastafari, although fundamentally there is no person or 'body' to permit or disallow believers to worship anyone in a movement which places individual spirituality at the centre of importance. The Bobo Shanti mansion of Rastafari typically venerate their founder King Emmanuel whilst 12 Tribes Members also venerate their founder Prophet Gad with some viewing them as supernatural beings. Marcus Garvey is also worshipped by some as a supernatural being.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

DRAFT

– Yes [specify]: Conceptions of Haile Selassie frequently paint him as a warrior and a conqueror, a vanquisher of injustice of the armies of evil and colonialism.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Prayer and veneration of the most high is often understood as a communication process. Haile Selassie has also communicated with some Rastafari in person, most prominently during his visit to Jamaica in 1966.

↳ In dreams:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Personal revelation is a very important source of spiritual truths for many Rastafari, usually taking the form of dramatic visions received both when sleeping and when in a state of daydreaming.

↳ In trance possession:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Possession by spiritual forces was a feature of the earliest Rastafari

communities, although these practices were largely expunged by a zealous form group known as the Youth Black Faith in the 1950's.

↳ Through divination practices:

DRAFT
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

DRAFT
– No

Notes: Rastafari worship and the procedures with in it are open to all, although priests do play roles of varying significance between different groups.

↳ Only through monarch

DRAFT
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

DRAFT
– Yes [specify]: The sacramental consumption of ganja (cannabis) is frequently understood as a process which elevates human consciousness to higher plane where communication with the divine is made easier and less encumbered.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

DRAFT
– No

Notes: Whilst belief in the presence of human spirits is commonplace in Jamaica most Rastafari eschew this as a dangerous superstition which detracts from the true divine nature of creation. Again, spirit veneration and interaction with spirits was common amongst early Rastafari communities but this was expunged by the Youth Black Faith in the 1950's.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

DRAFT
– No

Notes: Supernatural beings are frequently understood in human terms, although understanding and renderings of Jah vary considerably.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Many Rastafari understand Haile Selassie as a mixed human-divine being, 'Christ in his kingly form' as it is often stated. In this rendering his attributes are considered synonymous with the most high supreme God as described above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **atest**

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: atest

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: atest

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: atest

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Sacramental ganja (cannabis) consumption

Specific to this answer:
Region: atest

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: As previously mentioned various groups may venerate different humans but veneration is most frequently limited to these humans.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

DRAFT

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Large variance of beliefs on punishment meted out by supernatural beings. Many subscribe to a view that the unrighteous will meet their judgement in this world in a fiery blaze, whilst others subscribe to more traditionally Christian models that punishment will come in an afterlife.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jah is frequently understood as a God of justice and as the supreme arbiter. Implores are often made to Jah for the wicked to burn in a fiery damnation for their sins, particularly Babylon in the frequently heard phrase 'Babylon a burn'.

↳ Done only by high god:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

DRAFT

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Done randomly:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Other [specify]

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is meted out only to the wicked and evil doers.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Punishments in the after life aren't frequently emphasised by many Rastafari with an emphasis still very much in this realm. However many also have a more familiarly Judeo-Christian understanding of punishment in the afterlife.

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Other [specify]

DRAFT

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Divine punishment in this world is usually expressed through fire imagery with the understanding that the wicked can be met with immediate immolation by Jah if it is required. Punishment can be varied however with, effecting ones lot in life in different ways.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Other [specify]

DRAFT

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Jah is not generally understood as bestowing rewards as such, with a righteous life in communion with the Most High understand as a deeply rich and nourishing reward in itself. This varies however with some making direct appeals to Jah for rewards in their life.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Haile Selassie is most frequently understood as a messianic figure sent to the earth to emancipate humanity from the sufferation, bondage and evil enforced by Babylon. For some this comes in a Christian understanding of Selassie as the second coming of Christ, whilst other's consider him to be earth's first messiah. These groups also often link this to Haile Selassie's Solomonic heritage through the Ethiopian royal line which also connects him to King David. Many believe that after Haile Selassie's deposition as emperor in 1974 he is in a form of hiding somewhere either in this world or in another from where he will return in a second coming at some point in the future. Other's belief he is still present on earth in the much the same form as he was before. Some Rastafari would however reject this description of Haile Selassie as a Christian term which does reflect the divine nature of His Majesty, whilst other would suggest that Selassie was just a great man amongst men to have been on the earth (see linked video).

Reference: Hill, Robert A.. Dread History. Research Associates School Times, 2001.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Dread_History.html?hl=&id=SouBAAAACAAJ.

Reference: I Never Knew TV. "Prof-i on Haile Selassie Divine Status". YouTube, August 9, 2017.
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WqGdR_4AcjU.

Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

DRAFT

– Yes

Alive, identified:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

Coming on specified date:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Whilst Haile Selassie is a political figure his divine purpose is not understood as restoring political rule

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

DRAFT

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Understandings of the eschaton much like other aspects of Rastafari spirituality vary greatly. The movement has frequently been rendered as a millenarian group, but this description fails to capture the variety of interpretations amongst Rastafari. In a familiar Judeo-Christian framework some believe that the second coming of Haile Selassie will beckon in a judgement event in which the wicked are held to account for their evils and a new world order is enacted. In this, only the righteous will survive this event. Others believe that Selassie's presence on the earth represented the start of the eschaton in which the wicked are now held to account. Others still believe a super natural eschaton is unlikely and the earth and its residents will continue on its current trajectory. Between these positions are there countless other understandings of the end times.

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: **atest**

- ↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:
 - No

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: Many Rastafari state that it is only the truly righteous that will survive the judgement event

Specific to this answer:

Region: atest

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Social norms vary greatly between Rastafari communities, although many Jamaican Rastafari groups have understandings of different social norms between men and women. Women are frequently expected to cover their bodies in a way considered 'modest' and not intended to cause arousal. This often includes covering of the dreadlocks/hair. Attitudes towards menstruating women also vary, with some groups considering this group 'unclean' and therefore unable to engage in ritualistic and domestic practices particularly the preparation of food. Some Bobo Shanti groups consider women to be 'unclean' both a week before and after a week long menstruation period and therefore unable to engage with the wider group for the entirety of this period. Some groups also enforce a practice of women being unable to fully take part in some ritualistic practices at all times of the month. Some consider women unable to be 'true' Rastafari in their own right and only able to join the movement through a man, or 'kingman'. This view can also be applied to female children in Rastafari groups with it considered the duty of the group to 'grow a dawta', meaning a emphasised effort to ensure a young girl is properly raised in the ways of Rastafari that is not applied to boys. Women are also considered unable to take part in wider group 'reasoning' sessions by some, restricting females to reasoning only with each other. In group 'binghi' celebrations some groups also restrict women from being able to play the drums during this celebrations instead allowing them to play a shaker instead. All of this varies greatly however, with women taking a much greater and equal role in all aspects of community life in some Rastafari communities.

Reference: Vernan Success. "Women in Rastafari Documentary". YouTube, August 14, 2013. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=onalpomCEGU>.

Reference: Christensen, Jeanne. Rastafari Reasoning and the Rastawoman. Lexington Books, 2014. https://books.google.com/books/about/Rastafari_Reasoning_and_the_RastaWoman.html?hl=&id=CpJFAwAAQBAJ.

Reference: I Never Knew TV. "How to Dress Like a Rastafari Empress Youtube Video". YouTube, August 9, 2017. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WqGdR_4AcjU.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

DRAFT

– Present and clear

Notes: Many Rastafari have an understanding of some moral absolutes existing, most primarily love, generosity and support for the oppressed in the face of evil and hatred. This is frequently framed around a search for balance in everything and achieving balance within oneself and the universe. The most fundamental force uniting these moral absolutes is a desire to be living in communion with nature and with the earth as Jah intended it. Through this communion both humanity and nature will flourish.

Reference: I Never Knew TV. "Ras Stimulant Discussing Balance with Nature". YouTube, October 12, 2017. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LmFmNjIsXHE>.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Moral norms are most frequently attributed to the world order as put in place by Jah.

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

DRAFT

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

DRAFT

– Only one gender

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Righteousness, love and an engagement in fighting the forces of wickedness and oppression are considered centrally important by many Rastafari. Alongside these generosity, unity, independence of thought and spirit, and peaceability are also highly venerated.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

DRAFT
– No

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

DRAFT
– Yes

- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
DRAFT
– No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
DRAFT
– No
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
DRAFT
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
DRAFT
– No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
DRAFT
– No
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
DRAFT
– Yes [specify]: Love and peaceability

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

DRAFT
– No

Notes: Not emphasised although some priestly figures sometimes commit to a life of celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Monogamy is most frequently emphasised as an important aspect of a harmonious family unit and of a good upbringing for children. This is far from rigidly stuck to however amidst a Jamaican society in which multiple sexual partners is not uncommon. Women are also frequently held to a higher standard than men in this regard with it considered becoming of a woman to have multiple sexual partners.

Reference: Yawney, Carol. "Rastafarian Sistren by the Rivers of Babylon". *Canadian Journal of Woman Studies* 5, no. 2 (January 6, 1983).

↳ Monogamy (males):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

DRAFT

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

DRAFT

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

DRAFT

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Some fast in the literal avoidance of food completely for certain periods as an opportunity cleanse the body of a 'heaviness'. Others however understand fasting in a more Orthodox vein of avoidance of certain food groups. These practices are more common amongst Jamaica Bobo Shanti for whom many fast twice a week and also first Sunday of every month.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Rastafari attitudes and practices around food are deep and varied. The practices engaged with as part of this are often expressed as part of the 'ital' philosophy a central component of the wider concept of Rastafari 'livity'. In this alimentary context 'ital' manifests as a mode of eating which reduces harm to plant, planet and creature, emphasises the unity of all, and attempts to protect all life in as natural a state as is possible. This leads to a desire to consume organic, non-processed, low intervention and home/small scale farm grown wherever possible. Many Rastafari practice a vegan diet completely absent of any animal products in the view that these foodstuffs are produced through suffering and that things like milk and eggs represent elements of the reproductive cycles of other animals and so should not be used by humans. It is a common view that these foodstuffs represent the oppression of Jah's creation and so consumption of them would represent an impurity on the consumer. Others practice a vegetarian diet viewing the killing of animals as a serious transgression, whilst other frequently elder Rastafari eat fish citing the health benefits of its consumption. None engaged with on fieldwork in Jamaica ate meat however. Historically, many Rastafari in Jamaica practiced a specific prohibition against pork. Stemming initially from the Levitical code, this prohibition is similarly mirrored in Judaism, Islam and Orthodox Christianities such as Ethiopian Tewahedo. The historic place of pork consumption as a highly sacrilegious practice which serves to defile is well attested to. Hyperbolically, Sam Brown, a prominent Rastafari political activist, has referred to its consumption as 'outlaw[ed]'. Additionally, adherents retold stories of Rastafari in desperate situations instructing butchers to wrap them some of 'dat' whilst gesturing at the pork so as not to face up, at least verbally, to the transgression that is being committed. However, field work gave the impression that this element of Rastafari dietary practice has waned in its importance and centrality in a modern age where meat consumption on the whole is rare. There also

exists widespread prohibitions around salt. Salt avoidance offers some of the deepest historical roots of the practices within the Rastafari dietary ethic, and stands as one of the most widely observed in this study. Some followed what was termed a 'strictly Ital' philosophy, consuming no salt what so ever in the view that it is a needless adulteration of the food placed on this earth by Jah. This mentality is summed up astutely by Homiak, quoting a Jamaican Rastafari as stating 'de big question is, if I gi yuh some green banana right now fo' cook yuh gonna put salt in it. But if I gi yuh a ripe one yuh doan add nuttin to it. Yuh know dem kinda way deh?'. In its natural and ripe form in which the food entered creation nothing further need be added. Many Jamaica Rastafari also abstain from alcohol, citing its artificiality on a mass scale as the primary reason for this. Whilst the consumption of alcohol was not largely viewed as a major transgression, the imbuing of excessive amounts of alcohol that can lead to drunkenness was, with the brash and occasionally violent behaviour this can foster considered unbefitting of a peaceable Rastafari. Strength feeling on this topic also varies between the mansions, with 12 Tribes members usually taking a more liberal view. Tobacco is also regularly abstained from as a cancerous illness inducing substance in contrast to life giving ganja (cannabis). A strict avoidance of additives, preservatives and artificial flavourings is perhaps the most highly idealised of the core tenets amongst Rastafari dietary observance. As stated, the fundamental roots of the Ital philosophy lays in the belief that all food on the planet in its natural form is exactly as Jah intended it, and as such cannot be improved upon, only degraded, by human additions. Accordingly, any kind of flavouring, additive or preservative is seen as anathema and is to be avoided as much as is possible. Cans are also avoided for this reason, as well as their nutritionally deficient content and a suspicion of the metal container itself for possible chemical contamination risks. However, due to economic factors avoidance of these foodstuffs isn't always possible for some Rastafari particularly in urban areas. In Jamaica the ability to engage in these practices is very much determined by economic viability. During field work exploring Rastafari dietary practices it was frequently stated that what each individual Rastafari determines as their best option for eating when considering all factors involved in the decision (animal presence/health/economic situation) this should be respected and understood.

Reference: Powell, Joseph. "Ital Trod: An Examination of Rastafari Dietary (ietary) Practices". Unpublished Mphil Dissertation, n.d..

Reference: "Rasta Buru Discussing Ital", n.d.. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fCR8qoavZl>.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Most Jamaican Rastafari disapprove of piercings, tattoos and bodily modifications as adulterations of a body in its most ideal form as Jah created.

Reference: Ijahstars THE MINDSET. "Mutabaruka Discussing Tattoos". YouTube, October 11, 2019. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QxWeRxC5Fsc>.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

DRAFT

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

DRAFT

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

DRAFT

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

DRAFT

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Whilst many Jamaican Rastafari emphasise the importance of a non-materialistic outlook this not

required by most groups. This may vary for those joining more permanent Rastafari communities such as Bobo Hill in Bull Bay (Bobo Shanti).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

DRAFT

– No

Notes: With an emphasis on the individual spiritual journey of Rastafari there exists no formal requirements for attendance of services or meetings amongst Jamaican Rastafari. This does vary between specific groups however, with those based in more permanent communities and at Niyabinghi centres anticipated to contribute time more regularly.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

DRAFT

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Due to the heterogonous and decentralised nature of the movement there is no formal 'requirement' to accept the groups ethical practices. However Jamaican Rastafari frequently have no qualms about calling a purported member into question if they are not 'trodding' (following) the righteous ethical path of Rastafari.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Marginalisation is not a requirement of the group but historically this was a necessary result of members beginning to follow Rastafari practices in Jamaica, with many members ostracised by family members and society. In a modern age of greater recognition of the cultural value of Rastafari this is less prevalent.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Due to the heterogeneous and decentralised nature of the movement there are no formal 'requirements' to participate in any practices. However many Jamaican Rastafari would consider the sacramental consumption of Rastafari in a private or household setting with other Rastafari in a 'reasoning' session as an important element of worship.

Reference: "Guyanese Rastafari Discussing Reasoning", n.d.. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VbPCB3qvMmM>.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Due to the heterogeneous and decentralised nature of the movement there is no formal 'requirement' to take part in any practices. However, many Jamaican Rastafari would consider it important to participate in 'nyabinghi' or just 'binghi' celebrations to mark important anniversaries such as that of the Battle of Adowa, the coronation (transfiguration) of Haile Selassie, Ethiopian New Year and the birthdays (earthstrong) of Haile Selassie, Empress Menen and Marcus Garvey. Other groups engage in Sabbath binghi services weekly in which attendance is encouraged.

Reference: "Rastafari Binghi Celebration to Commemorate the Groundation (visit) of Haile Selassie to Jamaica", n.d.. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ne2Ju9K5ZyE>.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

DRAFT
– No

↳ Circumcision:

DRAFT
– No

↳ Food taboos:

DRAFT
– Yes

↳ Hair:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Rastafari are perhaps most visible from the outside for their dreadlocked hairstyles which a vast majority of Jamaican Rastafari adopt, matted or braided hair which runs down the body in long strands. This is considered a further extension of the natural design for the body in letting hair grow without cutting or grooming it. At some binghi celebrations both men and women may be expected to cover their hair in a tam (large usually knitted hat), or to wear them when entering the ceremony but for men to remove them during the service. The origin of this practice is unclear, with some theorising it arose out of the Nazarene vow (Num 6:1-21) which prohibits cutting of the hair whilst others attribute it to the Sadhu itinerant preachers of the Hindu faith who are likely to have been in present in Jamaica after arriving with indentured workers from India. Homiak and van Dijk attribute the popularisation of dreadlocks to the Youth Black Faith movement.

Reference: van Dijk Jan, Frank. "SOCIOLOGICAL MEANS: COLONIAL REACTIONS TO THE RADICALIZATION OF RASTAFARI IN JAMAICA, 1956-1959". *New West Indian Guide* 69, no. 1 (February 1, 1995).

↳ Dress:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Rastafari dress is very distinctive and serves as an important demarcator in Jamaica where members stand out clearly from their non-Rastafari counterparts. and this can vary between more casual and formal ceremonial occasions. The colours of the Ethiopian standard red, gold and green are frequently worn prominently by both men and women, with black also included by some in reference to the UNIA Pan African flag colours of red, black and green. Dress between men and women varies considerably. Casually, men are often seen either wearing a tam (knitted hat to cover the dreadlocks) in the colours described above or with a motif honouring a figure like Haile Selassie or a symbol such as the Star of David or the Conquering Lion of Judah, an often brightly coloured turban most commonly for Bobo Shanti members, dreadlocks tied up above the head or dreadlocks hanging low below the neck. Other than this Jamaican Rastafari men most frequently dress in typically Western urban clothes such as t shirts, vests, long sleeve shirts, jeans and shorts in Ethiopian/UNIA colour schemes or none, whilst some opt for more traditionally African attire such as a dashiki. On ceremonial occasions traditionally African wear is more common, and men will be often be expected to wear trousers and tams although tams are removed during some services. At Bobo Shanti ceremonies white is worn prominently by the priests along with turbans and crosses. Other adornments include badges featuring significant members and teachings of the movement, necklaces in natural materials such as wood, and wooden crosses in an Ethiopian Orthodox style. The dress of Jamaican Rastafari women is less variable than that of men, with moral standards around modesty more consistently expected and normatively applied. Many Jamaican Rastafari women will have their hair covered in either a tam or a turban/dhuku like cloth wrap. This will frequently be paired with a long dress down to the ankles, usually of the same fabric and pattern as the head covering. These patterns also include the Ethiopian/UNIA colour schemes, as well as colourful African patterns. These dress standards do also appear to have a generational aspect however, with older Rastafari women sticking more rigidly to these codes whilst younger Rastafari women can be seen without a head covering, shoulders uncovered and in more casual clothing more often. Badges, necklaces and crosses are also frequently worn by women. Appropriation of Rastafari dress is a concern for many Jamaican Rastafari who have seen their sacred symbols and colours taken by global companies, marketised and sold without any funds reaching the community from which they emanated. A walk down any market in Jamaica will offer t shirts emblazoned with Lion of Judah motifs and red, gold and green string vests on sale by non-Rastafari, something many Jamaican Rastafari consider inappropriate and financially exploitative.

Reference: Jaffe, Rivke. "Ital Chic: Rastafari, Resistance, and the Politics of Consumption in Jamaica". *Small Axe* 14, no. 1 (March 3, 2010). <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/374394>.

↳ Ornaments:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Ornaments such as pictures of Haile Selassie, Empress Menen and Marcus Garvey adorn many Rastafari houses in Jamaica. Ethiopian Orthodox art work is also frequently visible.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Some Jamaican Rastafari endeavour to learn Ge'ez or Amharic in order to more fully understand the original Ethiopian Orthodox writings but these are few in number.

↳ Other:

DRAFT

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari women will almost exclusively be referred to as 'Sis', 'Dawta' or 'Empress'. Men are also referred to as 'Brothers' or more commonly as 'Ras'.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

DRAFT

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Not emphasised although some priestly figures sometimes commit to a life of celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Monogamy is most frequently emphasised as an important aspect of a harmonious family unit and of a good upbringing for children. This is far from rigidly stuck to however amidst a Jamaican society in which multiple sexual partners is not uncommon. Women are also frequently held to a higher standard than men in this regard with it considered becoming of a woman to have multiple sexual partners.

Reference: Yawney, Carol. "Rastafarian Sistren by the Rivers of Babylon". *Canadian Journal of Woman Studies* 5, no. 2 (January 6, 1983).

↳ Monogamy (males):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

DRAFT
– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

DRAFT
– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

DRAFT
– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Some fast in the literal avoidance of food completely for certain periods as an opportunity cleanse the body of a 'heaviness'. Others however understand fasting in a more Orthodox vein of avoidance of certain food groups. These practices are more common amongst Jamaica Bobo Shanti for whom many fast twice a week and also first Sunday of every month.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Rastafari attitudes and practices around food are deep and varied. The practices engaged with as part of this are often expressed as part of the 'ital' philosophy a central component of the wider concept of Rastafari 'livity'. In this alimentary context 'ital' manifests as a mode of eating which reduces harm to plant, planet and creature, emphasises the unity of all, and attempts to protect all life in as natural a state as is possible. This leads to a desire to consume organic, non-processed, low intervention and home/small scale farm grown wherever possible. Many Rastafari practice a vegan diet completely absent of any animal products in the view that these foodstuffs are produced through suffering and that things like milk and eggs represent elements of the reproductive cycles of other animals and so should not be used by humans. It is a common view that these foodstuffs represent the oppression of Jah's creation and so consumption of them would represent an impurity on the consumer. Others practice a vegetarian diet viewing the killing of animals as a serious transgression, whilst other frequently elder Rastafari eat fish citing the health benefits of its consumption. None engaged with on fieldwork in Jamaica ate meat however. Historically, many Rastafari in Jamaica practiced a specific prohibition against pork. Stemming initially from the Levitical code, this prohibition is similarly mirrored in Judaism, Islam and Orthodox Christianities such as Ethiopian Tewahedo. The historic place of pork consumption as a highly sacrilegious practice which serves to defile is well attested to. Hyperbolically, Sam Brown, a prominent Rastafari political activist, has referred to its consumption as 'outlaw[ed]'. Additionally, adherents retold stories of Rastafari in desperate situations instructing butchers to wrap them some of 'dat' whilst gesturing at the pork so as not to face up, at least verbally, to the transgression that is being committed. However, field work gave the impression that this element of Rastafari dietary practice has waned in its importance and centrality in a modern age where meat consumption on the whole is rare. There also exists widespread prohibitions around salt. Salt avoidance offers some of the deepest historical roots of the practices within the Rastafari dietary ethic, and stands as one of the most widely observed in this study. Some followed what was termed a 'strictly ital' philosophy, consuming no salt what so ever in the view that it is a needless adulteration of the food placed on this earth by Jah. This mentality is summed up astutely by Homiak, quoting a Jamaican Rastafari as stating 'de big question is, if I gi yuh some green banana right now fo' cook yuh gonna put salt in it. But if I gi yuh a ripe one yuh doan add nuttin to it. Yuh know dem kinda way deh?'. In its natural and ripe form in which the food entered creation nothing further need be added. Many Jamaica Rastafari also abstain from alcohol, citing its artificiality on a mass scale as the primary reason for this. Whilst the consumption of alcohol was not largely viewed as a major transgression, the imbuing of excessive amounts of alcohol that can lead to drunkenness was, with the brash and occasionally violent behaviour this can foster considered unbecoming of a peaceable Rastafari. Strength feeling on this topic also varies between the mansions, with 12 Tribes members usually taking a more liberal view. Tobacco is also regularly abstained from as a cancerous illness inducing substance in contrast to life giving ganja (cannabis). A strict avoidance of additives, preservatives and artificial flavourings is perhaps the most highly idealised of the core tenets amongst Rastafari dietary observance. As stated, the fundamental roots of the Ital philosophy lays in the belief that all food on the planet in its natural form is exactly as Jah intended it, and as such cannot be improved upon, only degraded, by human additions. Accordingly, any kind of flavouring, additive or preservative is seen as anathema and is to be avoided as much as is possible. Cans are also avoided for this reason, as well as their nutritionally deficient content and a suspicion of the metal container itself for possible chemical contamination risks. However, due to economic factors avoidance of these foodstuffs isn't always possible for some Rastafari particularly in urban areas. In Jamaica the ability to engage in these practices is very much determined by economic viability. During field work exploring Rastafari dietary practices it was frequently stated that what each individual Rastafari determines as their best option

for eating when considering all factors involved in the decision (animal presence/health/economic situation) this should be respected and understood.

Reference: Powell, Joseph. "Ital Trod: An Examination of Rastafari Dietary (ietary) Practices". Unpublished Mphil Dissertation, n.d..

Reference: "Rasta Buru Discussing Ital", n.d.. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fCR8qoavZl>.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Most Jamaican Rastafari disapprove of piercings, tattoos and bodily modifications as adulterations of a body in its most ideal form as Jah created.

Reference: Ijahstars THE MINDSET. "Mutabaruka Discussing Tattoos". YouTube, October 11, 2019. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QxWeRxC5Fsc>.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

DRAFT

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

DRAFT

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

DRAFT

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

DRAFT

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Whilst many Jamaican Rastafari emphasise the importance of a non-materialistic outlook this not required by most groups. This may vary for those joining more permanent Rastafari communities such as Bobo Hill in Bull Bay (Bobo Shanti).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

DRAFT

– No

Notes: With an emphasis on the individual spiritual journey of Rastafari there exists no formal requirements for attendance of services or meetings amongst Jamaican Rastafari. This does vary between specific groups however, with those based in more permanent communities and at Niyabinghi centres anticipated to contribute time more regularly.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

DRAFT

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Due to the heterogonous and decentralised nature of the movement there is no formal 'requirement' to accept the groups ethical practices. However Jamaican Rastafari frequently have no qualms about calling a purported member into question if they are not 'trodding' (following) the righteous ethical path of Rastafari.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Marginalisation is not a requirement of the group but historically this was a necessary result of members beginning to follow Rastafari practices in Jamaica, with many members ostracised by family members and society. In a modern age of greater recognition of the cultural value of Rastafari this is less prevalent.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Due to the heterogeneous and decentralised nature of the movement there are no formal 'requirements' to participate in any practices. However many Jamaican Rastafari would consider the sacramental consumption of Rastafari in a private or household setting with other Rastafari in a 'reasoning' session as an important element of worship.

Reference: "Guyanese Rastafari Discussing Reasoning", n.d.. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VbPCB3qvMmM>.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Due to the heterogeneous and decentralised nature of the movement there is no formal 'requirement' to take part in any practices. However, many Jamaican Rastafari would consider it important to participate in 'nyabinghi' or just 'binghi' celebrations to mark important anniversaries such as that of the Battle of Adowa, the coronation (transfiguration) of Haile Selassie, Ethiopian New Year and the birthdays (earthstrong) of Haile Selassie, Empress Menen and Marcus Garvey. Other groups engage in Sabbath binghi services weekly in which attendance is encouraged.

Reference: "Rastafari Binghi Celebration to Commemorate the Groundation (visit) of Haile Selassie to Jamaica", n.d.. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ne2Ju9K5ZyE>.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

DRAFT

– Yes

Tattoos/scarification:

DRAFT

– No

Circumcision:

DRAFT

– No

Food taboos:

DRAFT

– Yes

Hair:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Rastafari are perhaps most visible from the outside for their dreadlocked hairstyles which a vast majority of Jamaican Rastafari adopt, matted or braided hair which runs down the body in long strands. This is considered a further extension of the natural design for the body in letting hair grow without cutting or grooming it. At some binghi celebrations both men and women may be expected to cover their hair in a tam (large usually knitted hat), or to wear them

when entering the ceremony but for men to remove them during the service. The origin of this practice is unclear, with some theorising it arose out of the Nazarene vow (Num 6:1-21) which prohibits cutting of the hair whilst others attribute it to the Sadhu itinerant preachers of the Hindu faith who are likely to have been in present in Jamaica after arriving with indentured workers from India. Homiak and van Dijk attribute the popularisation of dreadlocks to the Youth Black Faith movement.

Reference: van Dijk Jan, Frank. "SOCIOLOGICAL MEANS: COLONIAL REACTIONS TO THE RADICALIZATION OF RASTAFARI IN JAMAICA, 1956-1959". *New West Indian Guide* 69, no. 1 (February 1, 1995).

↳ Dress:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Rastafari dress is very distinctive and serves as an important demarcator in Jamaica where members stand out clearly from their non-Rastafari counterparts. and this can vary between more casual and formal ceremonial occasions. The colours of the Ethiopian standard red, gold and green are frequently worn prominently by both men and women, with black also included by some in reference to the UNIA Pan African flag colours of red, black and green. Dress between men and women varies considerably. Casually, men are often seen either wearing a tam (knitted hat to cover the dreadlocks) in the colours described above or with a motif honouring a figure like Haile Selassie or a symbol such as the Star of David or the Conquering Lion of Judah, an often brightly coloured turban most commonly for Bobo Shanti members, dreadlocks tied up above the head or dreadlocks hanging low below the neck. Other than this Jamaican Rastafari men most frequently dress in typically Western urban clothes such as t shirts, vests, long sleeve shirts, jeans and shorts in Ethiopian/UNIA colour schemes or none, whilst some opt for more traditionally African attire such as a dashiki. On ceremonial occasions traditionally African wear is more common, and men will be often be expected to wear trousers and tams although tams are removed during some services. At Bobo Shanti ceremonies white is worn prominently by the priests along with turbans and crosses. Other adornments include badges featuring significant members and teachings of the movement, necklaces in natural materials such as wood, and wooden crosses in an Ethiopian Orthodox style. The dress of Jamaican Rastafari women is less variable than that of men, with moral standards around modesty more consistently expected and normatively applied. Many Jamaican Rastafari women will have their hair covered in either a tam or a turban/dhuku like cloth wrap. This will frequently paired with a long dress down to the ankles, usually of the same fabric and pattern as the head covering. These patterns also include the Ethiopian/UNIA colour schemes, as well as colourful African patterns. These dress standards do also appear to have a generational aspect however, with older Rastafari women sticking more rigidly to these codes whilst younger Rastafari woman can be seen without a head covering, shoulders uncovered and in more casual clothing more often. Badges, necklaces and crosses are also frequently worn by women. Appropriation of Rastafari dress is concern for many Jamaican Rastafari who have seen their sacred symbols and colours taken by global companies, marketised and sold without any funds reaching the community from which they emanated. A walk down any market in Jamaica will offer t shirts emblazoned with Lion of Judah motifs and red, gold and green string vests on sale by non-Rastafari, something many Jamaican Rastafari consider inappropriate and financially exploitative.

Reference: Jaffe, Rivke. "Ital Chic: Rastafari, Resistance, and the Politics of Consumption in Jamaica". *Small Axe* 14, no. 1 (March 3, 2010). <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/374394>.

↳ Ornaments:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Ornaments such as pictures of Haile Selassie, Empress Menen and Marcus Garvey adorn many Rastafari houses in Jamaica. Ethiopian Orthodox art work is also frequently visible.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Some Jamaican Rastafari endeavour to learn Ge'ez or Amharic in order to more fully understand the original Ethiopian Orthodox writings but these are few in number.

↳ Other:

DRAFT

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari women will almost exclusively be referred to as 'Sis', 'Dawta' or 'Empress'. Men are also referred to as 'Brothers' or more commonly as 'Ras'.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

DRAFT

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

DRAFT

– A band

Notes: The Rastafari movement in Jamaica is highly decentralized and largely egalitarian. Specific communities such as the Bobo Shanti group in Bull Bay or 12 Tribes groups throughout the island will have slightly more formalised leadership structures usually featuring a community head.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Although famine is Jamaica is rare, the Jamaican Rastafari movement lacks the the centralised organisational structures to offer instituionalised famine relief. Rastafari community groups always endeavour to help out any of those in need.

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Given the decentralised and individualised nature of most Jamaican Rastafari a specific Rastafari formal education is most frequently not offered, with many Rastafari children taking part in state education. This has previously caused issues with some Rastafari parents being told their children's locks are incompatible with school dress codes. Jamaican Rastafari place a high value on a good education as the emancipator of the mind, and so emphasise it as crucial for Rastafari children in whichever form is selected. Exceptions to this do exist in more permanent Rastafari communities where a more informal homeschooling will be offered to children.

Reference: "Washington Post School Dreadlocks Article", August 29, 2018.

https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/the_americas/in-jamaica-a-5-year-old-girls-dreadlocks-are-at-the-center-of-a-supreme-court-battle/2018/08/28/5d435378-a7a7-11e8-ad6f-080770dcddc2_story.html.

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: The Jamaican Rastafari movement is heavily decentralised and features no formal bureaucracy. Groups such as the Ethiopian World Federation and the Caribbean Rastafari Organisation connect Jamaican Rastafari with other groups internationally. Smaller communities may also have small internal bureaucracies.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari communities outside of urban centres are centred around agriculture in an Ital mode, with communities largely self sufficient and able to provide food to all of its residents.

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: The decentralised and individualised nature of most Jamaican Rastafari mean that taxes and tithes are not a regular feature of life for many. Exceptions exist at binghi celebrations where donations might be requested but without obligation to pay. Equally more permanent communities of Rastafari may request more regular contributions from members.

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

DRAFT

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari emphasise the importance of love as a solution over violence and war. As such participation in any military, particularly one operated by a Babylonian governmental institution would be out of the question for a vast majority. Rastafari resistance against Babylon is often articulated in militaristic terms but this is a figurative expression.

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari place a heavy emphasis on the importance of agriculture, in any small or large scale, as central to their religious identity. Rastafari in Jamaica witnessed by the researcher made regular use of the nurturing soil and climate to provide themselves with a broad range of crops, from broad beans to pumpkins, and from ganja to basil. To these Rastafari the growth of plants was viewed as both sensible and spiritual, providing crops to either eat or sell whilst serving as a powerful experience of communion with Jah in the direct creation of life. This latter point was detailed at length, any many saw the process as central to their religious identity. From this, some Rastafari referred to a 'truth in nature', an objective truth both in our engagement with the earth and the philosophical lessons than can be drawn from it, an idea somewhat reminiscent of Thomist 'Natural Law'. Many stated that an essential part of the environmental notions contained within Rastafari dietary practice was a recognition of the symbiotic relationship between humanity and the planet. They stated that it is only when animal and plant life are working in harmony, for and with each other, that natural balance will be achieved. One small-scale farmer saw this as a direct transactional relationship, in stating that the positive energy one puts into the earth through the soil will be returned to oneself as good energy, both in the harvesting process and in the consumption of the food itself. With this in mind, almost all Jamaican Rastafari engaged with in field work provided food for themselves to some degree. This varies from a few potted plants on a windowsill to medium scale agricultural farms providing for whole communities. The fertile Jamaican soil and climate provides ample opportunity to grow many different kinds of crops, something almost all take direct advantage of. This almost exclusively takes the form of arable farming supplement by some foraging from that which grows wild in both urban and rural settings.

Reference: Powell, Joseph. "ital Trod: An Examination of Rastafari Dietary (ietary) Practices". Unpublished Mphil Dissertation, n.d..

Reference: "Ras Mokko Discussing Rastafari Farming", n.d..

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

DRAFT

– Gathering

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari possess a distinct dialect often referred to as Rastafari I-yaric, although this is a largely oral expression.

Reference: YouTube. "Rastafari Iyaric Vs Queen's English Biblical Interpretation". YouTube, n.d.. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zrLwDsFmVXg>.

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari largely follow the Gregorian Calendar with the groups own holy days included. A smaller number follow the Ethiopian Orthodox calendar.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT
– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Many urban Rastafari supplement their food intake with purchases from markets and when unavoidable supermarkets.

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

DRAFT
– Gathering

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT
– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: State institutions, although Jamaican Rastafari typically attempt to limit their interactions with the 'Babylonian' state and taxation system as far as possible given its perception as an evil and oppressive instrument.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Many Jamaican Rastafari receive state education.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

DRAFT
– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari have historically been greatly persecuted by the Jamaican Police Force who have viewed them as criminal pariahs intent on occasioning the downfall of society. In the early days of the Rastafari movement its most prominent preachers including Leonard Howell and Robert Hinds were imprisoned on charges of sedition for preaching the divinity of Haile Selassie. Due to this persecution Howell retreated from the urban areas of St Thomas in order to practice more freely and founded the first Rastafari community, Pinnacle. After years of largely self sufficient existence Pinnacle was raided and shut down by police militia in 1954 ostensibly due to the production of ganja (cannabis) at the site. In later years Jamaican Rastafari were victims of an institutionalised pogrom at the hands of the Jamaican Police and government authorities in the Coral Gardens Massacre in 1963, with Prime Minister Alexander Bustamante offering a bounty for each Rastafari brought to police stations dead or alive. Rastafari were assaulted, murdered, forcibly shaved of their locks in the street, lost property and were unable to access employment. In 2017 Prime Minister Andrew Holness officially apologised for the government's role in the massacre and agreed to set up a compensation fund for those affected by it. Discussions are still on going as to the realisation of this fund. Beyond Coral Gardens Jamaican Rastafari were viewed as social outcasts and essentially un-Jamaican through their allegiance to Haile Selassie. The group also continued to fall foul of the government's drug laws in their consumption and possession of ganja, and many were indicted and punished sometimes custodially for these crimes. In 2015 the Jamaican Government voted to decriminalise small scale cannabis possession and production. Despite this many Jamaican Rastafari still report harassment and infringements on rights from the Jamaican Police Force.

Reference: Ras Jahaziel Tafari. "Coral Gardens Massacre Documentary". YouTube, April 6, 2015. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wpRAUCRJRi0&t=1315s>.

Reference: James, Robertson. "That Vagabond George Stewart of England: Leonard Howell's Seditious Sermons, 1933-1941". In Leonard Percival Howell and the Genesis of Rastafari, 69-106, 2015. https://books.google.com/books/about/Leonard_Percival_Howell_and_the_Genesis.html?hl=&id=_UrjEACAAJ.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Ethiopian Orthodox Church for some

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: English

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari typically attempt to limit their interactions with the 'Babylonian' state as far as possible given it's perception as an evil and oppressive instrument. Historically and even through to some today this involved removing oneself from society completely and retreating to live in the hills in a completely self-sufficient agrarian existence refusing to handle 'Babylon's money' or even 'trod on Babylon's soil'. In a modern age of greater connectivity and reliance on state and industry structures this has become harder and less realised, with many now interacting with institutional bureaucracies when required.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

DRAFT

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Defence Force

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

DRAFT

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: The Jamaican Rastafari movement lacks the the centralised organisational structures to offer institutionalised famine relief. Community and charity groups such as the Word, Sound Power Collective offer poverty relief to elderly Rastafari through their Rastafari Ancient Supporting Fundraising.

Reference: Word Sound Power Collective. "Word Sound Power Collective". Word Sound Power Collective, n.d.. [https://www.wordsoundpowercollective.org/what-we-do#:~:text=What%20We%20Do%20%E2%80%94%20Word%20Sound%20Power%20Collective&text=as%20a%20501\(c\)3,Elders%20at%20](https://www.wordsoundpowercollective.org/what-we-do#:~:text=What%20We%20Do%20%E2%80%94%20Word%20Sound%20Power%20Collective&text=as%20a%20501(c)3,Elders%20at%20)

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: English/Jamaican Patwah

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: State infrastructure.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: State judicial system.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Poverty relief is available to Jamaican Rastafari through the governments UN and EU supported 'Poverty Reduction Programme'. Many Jamaican Rastafari are however suspicious of a government and it's programmes which has persecuted the movement for decades and may not be willing to accept support as such. Various Jamaican religious groups also offer poverty relief support which may be equally suspected.

Reference: Jamaica Information Service. "PIOJ Poverty Reduction Programme". Jamaica Information Service, March 22, 2018. <https://jis.gov.jm/pioj-launches-national-poverty-reduction-programme/>.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

DRAFT

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: The Jamaican Rastafari movement lacks the the centralised organisational structures to offer institutionalised care for the elderly and infirm. Community and charity groups such as the Word, Sound Power Collective offer support to elderly Rastafari through their Rastafari Ancient Supporting Fundraisings and Ancients Medical Assistance Fund.

Reference: Word Sound Power Collective. "Word Sound Power Collective". Word Sound Power Collective, n.d.. [https://www.wordsoundpowercollective.org/what-we-do#:~:text=What%20We%20Do%20%E2%80%94%20Word%20Sound%20Power%20Collective&text=as%20a%20501\(c\)3,Elders%20at%20](https://www.wordsoundpowercollective.org/what-we-do#:~:text=What%20We%20Do%20%E2%80%94%20Word%20Sound%20Power%20Collective&text=as%20a%20501(c)3,Elders%20at%20)

Reference: Majesty Media. "Ras Flako Discussing Word Sound Power Collective". YouTube, January 8, 2019. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L_fVpPcL3bU.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: The decentralised and individualised nature of most Jamaican Rastafari mean that instituionalised punishment structures do not feature for many Rastafari. Exceptions may exist in more permanent Rastafari communities in which punishments may exist for transgression of the groups moral or statutortial rules.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: State judicial enforcement

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

DRAFT

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: State infrastructure.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Support for the elderly and infirm is available through the Jamaican state although this requires 'at least 1,443 weeks of paid contributions, including an annual average of 39 weeks of paid or credited contributions', a condition which would disqualify many elderly Rastafari who have made a living from more casual modes of employment. Various Jamaican religious groups also offer care for the elderly and infirm.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

DRAFT

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican state legal codes

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

DRAFT

– A band

Notes: The Rastafari movement in Jamaica is highly decentralized and largely egalitarian. Specific communities such as the Bobo Shanti group in Bull Bay or 12 Tribes groups throughout the island will have slightly more formalised leadership structures usually featuring a community head.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Although famine in Jamaica is rare, the Jamaican Rastafari movement lacks the the centralised organisational structures to offer institutionalised famine relief. Rastafari community groups always endeavour to help out any of those in need.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: The Jamaican Rastafari movement lacks the the centralised organisational structures to offer institutionalised famine relief. Community and charity groups such as the Word, Sound Power Collective offer poverty relief to elderly Rastafari through their Rastafari Ancient Supporting Fundraising.

Reference: Word Sound Power Collective. "Word Sound Power Collective". Word Sound Power Collective, n.d. [https://www.wordsoundpowercollective.org/what-we-do#:~:text=What%20We%20Do%20%E2%80%94%20Word%20Sound%20Power%20Collective&text=as%20a%20501\(c\)3,Elders%20at%20](https://www.wordsoundpowercollective.org/what-we-do#:~:text=What%20We%20Do%20%E2%80%94%20Word%20Sound%20Power%20Collective&text=as%20a%20501(c)3,Elders%20at%20)

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Poverty relief is available to Jamaican Rastafari through the governments UN and EU supported 'Poverty Reduction Programme'. Many Jamaican Rastafari are however suspicious of a government and it's programmes which has persecuted the movement for decades and may not be willing to accept support as such. Various Jamaican religious groups also offer poverty relief support which may be equally suspected.

Reference: Jamaica Information Service. "PIOJ Poverty Reduction Programme". Jamaica Information Service, March 22, 2018. <https://jis.gov.jm/pioj-launches-national-poverty-reduction-programme/>.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: The Jamaican Rastafari movement lacks the the centralised organisational structures to offer institutionalised care for the elderly and infirm. Community and charity groups such as the Word, Sound Power Collective offer support to elderly Rastafari through their Rastafari Ancient Supporting Fundraisings and Ancients Medical Assistance Fund.

Reference: Word Sound Power Collective. "Word Sound Power Collective". Word Sound Power Collective, n.d. [https://www.wordsoundpowercollective.org/what-we-do#:~:text=What%20We%20Do%20%E2%80%94%20Word%20Sound%20Power%20Collective&text=as%20a%20501\(c\)3,Elders%20at%20](https://www.wordsoundpowercollective.org/what-we-do#:~:text=What%20We%20Do%20%E2%80%94%20Word%20Sound%20Power%20Collective&text=as%20a%20501(c)3,Elders%20at%20)

Reference: Majesty Media. "Ras Flako Discussing Word Sound Power Collective". YouTube, January 8, 2019. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L_fVPcP3bU.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Support for the elderly and infirm is available through the Jamaican state although this requires 'at least 1,443 weeks of paid contributions, including an annual average of 39 weeks of paid or credited contributions', a condition which would disqualify many elderly Rastafari who have made a living from more casual modes of employment. Various Jamaican religious groups also offer care for the elderly and infirm.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Given the decentralised and individualised nature of most Jamaican Rastafari a specific Rastafari formal education is most frequently not offered, with many Rastafari children taking part in state education. This has previously caused issues with some Rastafari parents being told their children's locks are incompatible with school dress codes. Jamaican Rastafari place a high value on a good education as the emancipator of the mind, and so emphasise it as crucial for Rastafari children in whichever form is selected. Exceptions to this do exist in more permanent Rastafari communities where a more informal homeschooling will be offered to children.

Reference: "Washington Post School Dreadlocks Article", August 29, 2018. https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/the_americas/in-jamaica-a-5-year-old-girls-dreadlocks-are-at-

the-center-of-a-supreme-court-battle/2018/08/28/5d435378-a7a7-11e8-ad6f-080770dcddc2_story.html.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Many Jamaican Rastafari receive state education.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

DRAFT
– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

DRAFT
– No

Notes: The Jamaican Rastafari movement is heavily decentralised and features no formal bureaucracy. Groups such as the Ethiopian World Federation and the Caribbean Rastafari Organisation connect Jamaican Rastafari with other groups internationally. Smaller communities may also have small internal bureaucracies.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari typically attempt to limit their interactions with the 'Babylonian' state as far as possible given its perception as an evil and oppressive instrument. Historically and even through to some today this involved removing oneself from society completely and retreating to live in the hills in a completely self-sufficient agrarian existence refusing to handle 'Babylon's money' or even 'trod on Babylon's soil'. In a modern age of greater connectivity and reliance on state and industry structures this has become harder and less realised, with many now interacting with institutional bureaucracies when required.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari communities outside of urban centres are centred around agriculture in an Ital mode, with communities largely self-sufficient and able to provide food to all of its residents.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT
– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

DRAFT
– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT
– Yes

Notes: State infrastructure.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

DRAFT
– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other

than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: State infrastructure.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: The decentralised and individualised nature of most Jamaican Rastafari mean that taxes and tithes are not a regular feature of life for many. Exceptions exist at binghi celebrations where donations might be requested but without obligation to pay. Equally more permanent communities of Rastafari may request more regular contributions from members.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: State institutions, although Jamaican Rastafari typically attempt to limit their interactions with the 'Babylonian' state and taxation system as far as possible given its perception as an evil and oppressive instrument.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

DRAFT

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari have historically been greatly persecuted by the Jamaican Police Force who have viewed them as criminal pariahs intent on occasioning the downfall of society. In the early days of the Rastafari movement its most prominent preachers including Leonard Howell and Robert Hinds were imprisoned on charges of sedition for preaching the divinity of Haile Selassie. Due to this persecution Howell retreated from the urban areas of St Thomas in order to practice more freely and founded the first Rastafari community, Pinnacle. After years of largely self sufficient existence Pinnacle was raided and shut down by police militia in 1954 ostensibly due to the production of ganja (cannabis) at the site. In later years Jamaican Rastafari were victims of an institutionalised pogrom at the hands of the Jamaican Police and government authorities in the Coral Gardens Massacre in 1963, with Prime Minister Alexander Bustamante offering a bounty for each Rastafari brought to police stations dead or alive. Rastafari were assaulted, murdered, forcibly shaved of their locks in the street, lost property and were unable to access employment. In 2017 Prime Minister Andrew Holness officially apologised for the government's role in the massacre and agreed to set up a compensation fund for those affected by it. Discussions are still on going as to the realisation of this fund. Beyond Coral Gardens Jamaican Rastafari were viewed as social outcasts and essentially un-Jamaican through their allegiance to Haile Selassie. The group also continued to fall foul of the government's drug laws in their consumption and possession of ganja, and many were indicted and punished sometimes custodially for these crimes. In 2015 the Jamaican Government voted to decriminalise small scale cannabis possession and production. Despite this many Jamaican Rastafari still report harassment and infringements on rights from the Jamaican Police Force.

Reference: Ras Jahaziel Tafari. "Coral Gardens Massacre Documentary". YouTube, April 6, 2015. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wpRAUCRJrI0&t=1315s>.

Reference: James, Robertson. "That Vagabond George Stewart of England: Leonard Howell's Seditious Sermons, 1933-1941". In Leonard Percival Howell and the Genesis of Rastafari, 69-106, 2015. https://books.google.com/books/about/Leonard_Percival_Howell_and_the_Genesis.html?hl=&id=_-UrgEACAAJ.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

DRAFT

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: State judicial system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: The decentralised and individualised nature of most Jamaican Rastafari mean that institutionalised punishment structures do not feature for many Rastafari. Exceptions may exist in more permanent Rastafari communities in which punishments may exist for transgression of the groups moral or statutory rules.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: State judicial enforcement

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

DRAFT

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

DRAFT

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican state legal codes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari emphasise the importance of love as a solution over violence and war. As such participation in any military, particularly one operated by a Babylonian governmental institution would be out of the question for a vast majority. Rastafari resistance against Babylon is often articulated in militaristic terms but this is a figurative expression.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s)

other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Defence Force

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari possess a distinct dialect often referred to as Rastafari I-yaric, although this is a largely oral expression.

Reference: YouTube. "Rastafari Iyaric Vs Queen's English Biblical Interpretation". YouTube, n.d.. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zrLwDsFmVXg>.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: English

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: English/Jamaican Patwah

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

DRAFT

– No

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari largely follow the Gregorian Calendar with the groups own holy days included. A smaller number follow the Ethiopian Orthodox calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Ethiopian Orthodox Church for some

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Jamaican Rastafari place a heavy emphasis on the importance of agriculture, in any small or large scale, as central to their religious identity. Rastafari in Jamaica witnessed by the researcher made regular use of the nurturing soil and climate to provide themselves with a broad range of crops, from broad beans to pumpkins, and from ganja to basil. To these Rastafari the growth of plants was viewed as both sensible and spiritual, providing crops to either eat or sell whilst serving as a powerful experience of communion with Jah in the direct creation of life. This latter point was detailed at length, any many saw the process as central to their religious identity. From this, some Rastafari referred to a 'truth in nature', an objective truth both in our engagement with the earth and the philosophical lessons than can be drawn from it, an idea somewhat reminiscent of Thomist 'Natural Law'. Many stated that an essential part of the environmental notions contained within Rastafari dietary practice was a recognition of the symbiotic relationship between humanity and the planet. They stated that it is

only when animal and plant life are working in harmony, for and with each other, that natural balance will be achieved. One small-scale farmer saw this as a direct transactional relationship, in stating that the positive energy one puts into the earth through the soil will be returned to oneself as good energy, both in the harvesting process and in the consumption of the food itself. With this in mind, almost all Jamaican Rastafari engaged with in field work provided food for themselves to some degree. This varies from a few potted plants on a windowsill to medium scale agricultural farms providing for whole communities. The fertile Jamaican soil and climate provides ample opportunity to grow many different kinds of crops, something almost all take direct advantage of. This almost exclusively takes the form of arable farming supplement by some foraging from that which grows wild in both urban and rural settings.

Reference: Powell, Joseph. "Ital Trod: An Examination of Rastafari Dietary (ietary) Practices". Unpublished Mphil Dissertation, n.d..

Reference: "Ras Mokko Discussing Rastafari Farming", n.d..

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- DRAFT**
- Gathering
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- DRAFT**
- Yes

Notes: Many urban Rastafari supplement their food intake with purchases from markets and when unavoidable supermarkets.

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- DRAFT**
- Gathering
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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